

Original Research Article

Association between Life Satisfaction and Academic Achievement among Nursing Students at the University of Lahore, Pakistan

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Abstract

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Life satisfaction is influenced by daily stress, happiness, health condition, and personal qualities, which in turn are influenced by a number of other factors. Academic success is widely assessed through the use of tests and ongoing levels of assessments, according to research, however there is no universal agreement in this field. A correlational study design was used to identify association between Life satisfaction and Academic achievement among nursing students. The site is the overall location for the research. The study site was The University of Lahore New Campus. A correlational study was done on 120 both female and male nursing students after informed consent. Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Academic achievement and life satisfaction have a considerable or significant association, according to the findings. However, there were no gender differences among nursing students. Participants of study were n= 120. 120 male and female includes, 82 female and 38 male included. Ages of participants were 18 years to 23 years of age. The main determinant of this study to assess association between Life satisfaction and Academic achievement among nursing students. Nursing students have a positive association between Life satisfaction and Academic achievement.

Keywords: Life Satisfaction, Academic Achievement, Nursing Students

INTRODUCTION

A high standard of living correlates to a variety of favorable life outcomes. Individuals appreciate healthy relationships, inexpensive housing, and a good security system in modern times. The value of subjective experience has grown over time. The state of one's health is investigated. Maslow's theory was first proposed in the early 1940s. Self-actualization theory is a concept that relates to basic human needs. Human wants are described as being "very variable," with "many requirements being met" present in a person at the same time (Caz and Tanyeri, 2018).

According to a new study, high life satisfaction is linked to favourable outcomes such as psychological well-being, interpersonal relationships, and academic success accomplishment (Caz and Tanyeri, 2018).

There are many factors that affect the quality of life and satisfaction for a human being i.e.: Education, Job. Greater highly educated countries, on average, have more resources, better levels of enjoyment, but education also brings opportunities for advancement. Recent research has focused on age disparities in life satisfaction projections, the accuracy of predicted future life satisfaction across adulthood, and the age differential impacts of educational attainment, as well as health resources ("Academic Achievement and Life Satisfaction Among Medical Students with Forced Medical Parental Choice," 2019).

The factors that influence young adults' life satisfaction Students' job choices are marked by a variety of factors. A high level of emotional turmoil as well as a wide variety

of dangers and possibilities. It has also been discovered that moderating elements such as school environment, parental methods, and other factors have a role. Since the 1980s, family therapists, career counselors, and others have found vital and crucial facts regarding the relevance of parents choosing their children's careers. Even though adolescents begin to exhibit independence in terms of their schooling at an early age, the majority of them remain dependent on their parents until their young adulthood, which covers the ages of 18 to 25 ("Academic Achievement and Life Satisfaction Among Medical Students with Forced Medical Parental Choice," 2019).

Academic Achievement

Academic success is widely assessed through the use of tests and ongoing levels of assessments, according to research, however there is no universal consensus in this field (Crede, 2015). Despite the fact that instructional determination has been addressed from a variety of conceptual perspectives, a great number of current researchers have used the self-dedication idea. Self-determined concepts are a comprehensive theoretical framework that explains global, contextual, and individual stimuli ("Academic Achievement and Life Satisfaction Among Medical Students with Forced Medical Parental Choice," 2019).

Life satisfaction

According to research, life satisfaction might represent an individual's level of happiness with their living situation. People might be motivated to achieve their goals and objectives as a result of these encounters ("Academic Achievement and Life Satisfaction Among Medical Students with Forced Medical Parental Choice," 2019). These aspects include self-acceptance, interpersonal relationships, environmental mastery, and so on. Autonomy in carrying out daily tasks, a sense of purpose in life, and a level of personal development. The life of a person who scores highly on these categories has a greater level of psychological well-being (Jayawickreme, 2004).

Aim of Study

The aim of this study was to assess the association between life satisfaction and academic achievement among nursing students at the University of Lahore.

Research Questions

What is the association between Life Satisfaction

academic achievements among nursing students?

Significance of study

The goal of this research is to see if there is a demonstrable link between academic accomplishment and student satisfaction. Support for basic psychological needs is vital for intrinsic rather than extrinsic motivation, academic accomplishment, and life satisfaction, according to a self-determination view on human motivation. Self-determination as fulfillment of the three universal, innate, and psychological requirements for competence, autonomy, and relatedness is critical for individual well-being.

Hypothesis

There would be a significant relationship between life satisfaction and academic achievement among nursing students.

There would be significant gender inequalities among students of nursing in terms of academic achievement and life satisfaction.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design

The correlational study design was used in this Study

Setting

The setting of this study was conducted at the Lahore School of Nursing, University of Lahore.

Study population

Nursing Students of the University of Lahore.

Sampling Method

Randomized Sampling technique was used for data collection.

Sample Size

By using Solvin's formula, the sample size was concluded at 120.

$$n = N \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{Ne^2}}$$

n=sample size

N=population size
E=margin error (0.05)
 $n=N/1+N(0.05)^2$
n=120

Inclusion criteria

Following are included in Data collection

- The age range of the sample was 18 to 23 years.
- Students of BSN 1st year and 2nd year.
- The students of the Nursing department.
- Those who were willing to participate.

Exclusion criteria

Following are excluded in data collection

- Those who were not willing to participate in this study.
- Students of MSN, PBSN and BSN(3rd,4th year).
- Those who attended training programmes and workshops.

Data Collection Plan

Data collection plan is one of the main sources to collect data. An adopted questionnaire was used to collect data from the study participants. The permission was taken from participants. There was given time and a free hand to complete it and return it.

Research tool

A well-structured questionnaire with Likert scale adopted to assess association between life satisfaction and academic achievement among nursing students. Questionnaire consisted of two parts: the first part explained the consent form and demographic data of participants in which name, Age, academic year, and other parts of the questionnaire clarified the questions.

Ethical Consideration

During the research, ethical considerations were taken into account.

- The university provided a permission letter.
- The purpose was explained to the participants.
- The participants were asked to sign a written consent form.

Data analysis

Data analysis was be done by SPSS version 25. Statistical computer software for data analysis. The study was correlational study and all the statistics were obtained through the SPSS software.

RESULTS

Data collected from Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, Lahore to check `Association between Life Satisfaction and Academic Achievement among Nursing Students` correlational study interviewed by 120 nursing students in Lahore School of Nursing. The response rate of the survey was 100% and the age range was under 10 to 23 years female and male. Female and male participants were included. The data analysis consists of two parts, the first part includes demographic data that completely describes the demographic variable and the second part provides descriptive analyses which provide us `r` and `p` values of respondents regarding 16 questionnaires. Table 1

Above table 2 shows that participants of study were n= 120. 120 male and female includes, 82 female and 38 male included. Ages of participants were 18 years to 23 years of age.

Mean and Std. Deviation of Age, gender and year of respondents. The below table shows the correlation between life satisfaction and academic achievement (N=120)

Pearson correlation test was applied to check the association or relationship between life satisfaction and academic achievement. Table-8 indicates that r .423 and p value is 0.0001. There isa positive relationship 0.0423 between life satisfaction and academic achievement with significance 0.0001 of A significant relationship between life satisfaction and academic achievement r=.423 and p is 0.0001.

The mean and standard deviation of age, gender and year. Mean and standard deviation of age is (Mean=1.4833, Std. deviation=.50182), for gender mean and standard deviation as (Mean=16833, Std. deviation=.46713) and mean and standard deviation for year is (Mean=1.3917, Std. deviation=.49017).

DISCUSSION

The current study assesses the association between Life satisfaction and academic achievement of 120 nursing students, The University of Lahore, both male and female aged 18 years to 23 years from The University of Lahore. The goal of this study was to look into the relationship between academic accomplishment and life satisfaction in nursing students. In addition, the study examined gender differences among the participants. Another goal

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the study participants

	Group	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Age	18-20 years	62	51.7
	21-23 years	58	48.3
	Total	120	120
Gender	Female	82	68.33
	Male	38	31.7
	Total	120	120
Education	1 st year BScN	73	60.8
	2 nd year BScN	47	39.2
	Total	120	120

Table 2. Mean and Std. Deviation

	Age of respondents	Gender of respondents	Year of respondents
N Valid	120	120	120
Mean	1.4833	1.6833	1.3917
Std. Deviation	.50182	.46713	.49017

Table 3. Correlation between life satisfaction and academic achievement (N=120)

		Life Satisfaction	Academic Achievement
Life Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.423**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	120	120
Academic achievement	Pearson Correlation	.423**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	120	120

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

of the research was to evaluate the association between academic achievements. Several studies and findings show a strong link between student life satisfaction and academic achievement (Sadia Firdous, 2019). There is numerous more research that back up the idea that academic achievement and life satisfaction are linked. Redman, Saltman; et.al (2004) investigated the factors that influence medical students' job choices and life happiness. In light of the findings, it has been established that academic accomplishment and life satisfaction are inextricably linked. Roeser and Peck (2009) investigated the impact of self-awareness, metacognition, parenting, and other demographic characteristics on student academic attainment. It's important to remember that students' academic performance and perception of academic achievement are impacted by a variety of factors such as self-efficacy, self-awareness.

The findings show that among high achievers, there is no substantial link between life satisfaction and academic achievement. The findings of this study are in line with those of previous investigations. In the first section of the

study, the majority of respondents indicated a moderately high degree of life satisfaction, which is consistent with prior studies on adult and college student satisfaction (Civitci and Civitci, 2015). There are an infinite number of learning experiences that impact career choice. However, one major factor in this regard is parental choice. It has been found that in a large number of cases, parental choice is forced upon students. This is mainly because of the fact that parents are the ones who finance the education of their children in a large number of cases. Gives information on the relationship between the four extended life satisfaction domains and academic achievement on the total life satisfaction of high achievers. There is no significant association between overall life satisfaction and academic achievement, according to the findings; $r = -0.155$, $p=0.309$. The findings revealed that there is a strong association between each domain of life happiness and academic progress for each domain (Azyyati Zakaria,2016).

For nursing students, a determining factor at times when they are not able to make a decision on their own.

The results of this study show that a partially negative relation between age, gender, year and academic achievement, there is positive relation between life satisfaction and age, year of nursing students. Findings also show a positive relation between academic achievement and life satisfaction.

Limitations

- This education set a lot of boundaries; the phase period was short.
- It was a correlational study. Pearson's test should be conducted.
- Randomized sampling technique was applied for data collection.
- A Smaller number of respondents was included in this study.

CONCLUSION

This research about nursing students' relationship between Life satisfaction and academic achievement in The University of Lahore. The main determinant of this study to assess association between Life satisfaction and Academic achievement among nursing students. A questionnaire dispersed among nursing students in The University of Lahore. Collected data of this study was analyzed by SPSS version 25. The end results of this research show that nursing students have a positive association between Life satisfaction and Academic achievement.

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